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ОСОБЕННОСТИ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ НОВЫХ ФАЗ ПРИ СИНТЕЗЕ СОЕДИНЕНИЙ $BaTi_{(1-x)}Zr_{(x)}O_3$ ИЗ ПОРОШКОВ $BaCO_3+TiO_2+ZrO_2$

PECULIARITIES OF THE PHASE FORMATION IN THE SYNTHESIS OF $BaTi_{(1-x)}Zr_{(x)}O_3$ COMPOUNDS FROM $BaCO_3+TiO_2+ZrO_2$ POWDERS

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В данной статье представлены результаты произведенного синтеза порошков твердых растворов $BaTi_{(1-x)}Zr_{(x)}O_3$ из смесей $BaCO_3+TiO_2+ZrO_2$ методом твердотельной реакции с двухэтапным прогревом при температуре 800-1200°C. В результате получены соединения $BaTiO_3$ и $BaZr_{0,25}Ti_{0,75}O_3$, концентрация и параметры кристаллических решеток которых определяются режимом синтеза. Произведен рентгенофазовый анализ состава полученных соединений. На основе полученных данных сделан вывод, что с увеличением температуры прогрева концентрация фазы $BaZr_{0,25}Ti_{0,75}O_3$ увеличивается.

This article presents the results of the synthesis of powders of solid solutions of $\text{Bi}(1-x)\text{Zr}(x)\text{O}_3$ from mixtures of $\text{BaCO}_3+\text{TiO}_2+\text{ZrO}_2$ by a solid-state reaction method with two-stage heating at a temperature of 800-1200°C. As a result, compounds BaTiO_3 and $\text{BaZr}_{0,25}\text{Ti}_{0,75}\text{O}_3$ were obtained, the concentration and parameters of the crystal lattices of which are determined by the synthesis mode. X-ray phase analysis of the composition of the obtained compounds was performed. Based on the data obtained, it is concluded that with an increase in the heating temperature, the concentration of the $\text{BaZr}_{0,25}\text{Ti}_{0,75}\text{O}_3$ phase increases.

Ключевые слова: титанат-цирконат бария, рентгенофазовый анализ, термостабилизирующие покрытия, синтез, структура.

Key words: barium titanate-zirconate, X-ray diffraction analysis, thermal control coatings, synthesis, structure.

Introduction. Barium titanate powders can be used as thermal control coating pigment capable of stabilizing the temperature of the objects on which it is applied due to a change of the emissivity in the region of the Curie point. When the coating is heated to the phase transition temperature, its emissivity increases sharply, which leads to an increase of the radiated energy and a decrease of the coating temperature. Conversely, when the coating temperature drops below the operating temperature, an abrupt drop in emissivity occurs. This leads to a decrease in the radiated energy and, accordingly, to an increase in temperature to the previous level. This is the basis for the principle of temperature stabilization of the object, on the surface of which there is a stabilizing coating.

The Curie point of barium titanates corresponds to a temperature of 120–130°C [1,2]. Above this temperature, BaTiO_3 has a cubic lattice. With a decrease of temperature the phase transition (PT) undergoes into a tetragonal ($5^\circ\text{C} \leq T \leq 120^\circ\text{C}$), rhombic ($-90^\circ\text{C} \leq T \leq 5^\circ\text{C}$) and rhombohedral ($T < 90^\circ\text{C}$) lattice. In accordance with this, the electrical [3,4], dielectric [5,6], and optical [7,8] properties change. The greatest changes in these properties occur in the region of the Curie point, in the region of the phase transition from cubic to tetragonal lattice: electrical conductivity (σ) can vary by more than 5 orders of magnitude [3,4], permittivity (ϵ) - by several times [5-7]. In this case, the optical properties may also change [8, 9]. Partial substitution of titanium cations by atoms of other elements makes it possible to shift the Curie point and PT to the low-temperature region. The magnitude of the shift and characteristics of the phase transition are determined by the type and concentration of substituting atoms.

Thus, the study of the composition, structure, and concentration of compounds formed during the solid-state synthesis of barium titanates with partially substituted cations is of scientific and practical interest. The purpose of this work is to study the phase composition of compounds formed during heating in the temperature range 800-1200 °C of mixtures of $\text{BaCO}_3+\text{TiO}_2+\text{ZrO}_2$ powders.

Materials and Methods

To synthesize $\text{BaTi}_{(1-x)}\text{Zr}_{(x)}\text{O}_3$ compounds the BaCO_3 powder of a pure grade ("ch" grade) as per the Russian Federal Standard (GOST) 4158-80 manufactured by "Vekton" CJSC, TiO_2 powder of Solikamsky used for household paints and ZrO_2 powder of an extra pure grade ("os. ch. 9-2" grade) were used. The composition of the powders: - BaCO_3 (mass fraction of the main substance - not less than 99, sulfates - 0.2, residue insoluble in hydrochloric acid - 0.2, chlorides in terms of Cl - 0.05, iron - 0.005); - TiO_2 (mass fraction of the main substance - not less 98, Fe_2O_3 - 0.03, SiO_2 - 0.3, volatile substances - 0.5); - ZrO_2 (mass fraction of the main substance - not less than 98, sulfates -0.05, chlorides - 0.02, iron - 0.004, potassium -0.004, silicon -0.004, sodium -0.004, titanium - 0.004). The powders were mixed in the required proportion, dispersed in distilled water using a PE-6100 magnetic stirrer, the resulting solution was evaporated in an oven at 150°C for 6 hours, then the mixture was ground in an agate mortar and heated in a SNOL-1,4,2,5.1,2/12,5-II chamber electric furnace, at a temperature of 800 °C, 1000 °C and 1200 °C for 5 hours. After heating, the result-

ing mixture was ground again in an agate mortar. A mixture was prepared with the ratio of mass parts BaCO₃:TiO₂:ZrO₂ corresponding to the BaZr_{0.25}Ti_{0.75}O₃ compound. The structure and phase composition of the powders were studied using a Shimadzu XRD 6000 LabX X-ray diffractometer.

Results and discussion

The diffraction patterns of the powders obtained as a result of the synthesis are shown in Fig. 1. From the analysis of the diffraction spectra the percentage of phases was established (Table 1). It can be seen from Fig. 1a that at synthesis temperature of 800 °C, the BaCO₃, TiO₂, and ZrO₂ components do not completely react. The residual concentration of the initial compounds is, wt %: BaCO₃ -34.3, ZrO₂ -28.6, TiO₂ - 17.8 (Table 1).

At the synthesis temperature of 1000°C, the BaCO₃ and TiO₂ compounds react completely, only ZrO₂ in an amount of 5.2 wt.% remains partially unreacted. The concentration of barium titanate increases from 17.7 wt.% to 63.8 wt.%. ZrTiO₄ is formed in the amount of 29.9 wt.%.

The concentration of ZrTiO₄ increases with increasing temperature from 800 to 1000°C, and with a further increase to 1200°C this compound is practically absent (C=1 wt.%). Its decrease is determined by the fact that up to a temperature of 1000°C the main phase BaZr_{0.25}Ti_{0.75}O₃ is not yet formed, and at T=1200°C its concentration already reaches high values, i.e. the components of the mixture at this temperature are consumed to form a compound with three cations.

Fig. 1. X-ray diffraction patterns of compounds obtained by synthesis from mixtures of BaCO₃ + TiO₂ + ZrO₂ micropowders by heating for 5 hours at a temperature, °C: (a) 800, (b) 1000, and (c) 1200.

Table 1. Dependence of the concentration (wt %) of the compounds formed during the synthesis by heating for 5 h of mixtures of BaCO₃ + TiO₂ + ZrO₂ powders on the synthesis temperature.

Compound	Synthesis temperature, °C		
	800	1000	1200
BaTiO ₃	17,7	63,8	57,1
BaZr _{0.25} Ti _{0.75} O ₃	1,6	0,8	33,3
ZrTiO ₄	0	29,9	1
ZrO ₂	28,6	5,2	8,5

An increase of the energy of the reactive mixture with an increase of the heating temperature to 1000°C leads to the fact that, in addition to this, other reactions also occur, which leads to a decrease in the concentration of the $\text{BaZr}_{0.25}\text{Ti}_{0.75}\text{O}_3$ phase. Such a reaction is the formation of a new compound ZrTiO_4 , which includes two cations Zr^{4+} and Ti^{4+} . The phase yield increases to 29.9 wt. %.

The performed studies have shown that the synthesis temperature of 1200°C is optimal and sufficient to obtain compounds that determine the phase transition and its shifting to the low-temperature region compared to the Curie point of barium titanate. Both BaTiO_3 and BaTiZrO_3 compounds in this powder will determine the temperature dependence of electrical, dielectric, optical, and other properties [3–9]. Their total concentration at this synthesis temperature for 5 hours of mixtures of $\text{BaCO}_3 + \text{TiO}_2 + \text{ZrO}_2$ powders is 90.4%.

The remainder in this powder is determined by the unreacted ZrO_2 . It can play an additional protective role in this powder. If the ZrO_2 nanopowder is used instead of micropowder at the same concentration in a mixture of powders, then unreacted nanoparticles can act as relaxation centers for defects formed in this powder under various external influences. Such nanoparticles are of particular importance under the action of radiation on various compounds. For example, the deposition of nanoparticles on the surface of grains and granules of zinc oxide powders [10, 11] and other oxide powders [12] leads to a significant increase in their radiation resistance.

Thus, in order to obtain a powder with a controlled phase transition of the electrical, dielectric, and optical properties temperature dependencies, it is necessary to carry out its synthesis by heating mixtures of $\text{BaCO}_3 + \text{TiO}_2 + \text{ZrO}_2$ powders for 5 hours at 1200°C. The resulting powder will consist of 90.4 wt. % of BaTiO_3 and BaTiZrO_3 compounds.

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